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DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

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PEOPLE ORGANIZIMDA OCCURRING PITUITARY TUMORS

Samarkand State Medical Heniversiteti Medical pedagogy faculty of 404-
group students

Pardayeva Umidaxon Yaxshimurod qizi

Shukurova Nargiza Qarshi qizi

Academic leader: **Qurbonova Nozima Sobirjonovna**

THE UZBEKISTAN

Annotatsiya: Pituitary tumors what is it?

Pituitary tumor-an abnormal growth in the pituitary gland this.The pituitary is a small gland in the brain. It is located on the back of the nose. This function produces hormones which affect many other glands and many reaches of your body.Pituitary tumors the majority of cancer (benign) are not.They are your body other parts does not spread.However, they in pituitary too little or too much hormone form to take cause you can, that while in the body problems causing produces.Too many hormones work out which pituitary tumors other glands more hormones yield to be taken comes.This own specific hormone each one with associated symptoms causing produces.Many pituitary tumor near surrounding the optic nerves also click.In this view the problems causing you to be out in.Pituitary tumors the majority of symptoms causing out does not.As a result, they the diagnosis is not put.Or they are just the brain's regular vision testing during the found.Of the people, about 25% did not know in case of small pituitary tumors able to be may.Below pituitary tumors are the main types are listed.

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Keywords: Null cells adenomali, tumors, and pituitary.

Ma'qolasiga content: who do not work adenomalar (null cells adenomali).

These tumors most widely spread type is. They additional hormone yield does not. The tumor was certain a size able until you never how can a sign be can. The tumor is sufficiently large if the home headache and vision problems lead cause can. Pituitary large tumors common pituitary cells to be crushed can. This hormone production is the production of a decrease as a result of came out which sign to get come.

Prolactin-producing tumors (prolaktinomalar).

These benign tumors are also common. They will make too much prolactin. If you are a woman, or even be an undisciplined your menstrual period menstruation to see high levels of prolactin can be stopped. These tumors, even if pregnant or nursing mother's milk can cause to prepare. If you are male, you can be erectile disfunktsiya or lack of interest in sex. Also, in breast enlargement, body hair can be low or less of the amount of sperm. With the passage of time you can be headaches and vision problems.

ACTH-producing tumors.

ACTH (adrenokortikotropik hormone) which stimulates the production of adrenal steroids affect metabolism bezini. Them glyukokortikoidlar is called. They have the entire body, redness and swelling (inflammation) will reduce. They're your immunity your slows down. Too much ACTH cushing's disease causing out can. This disease of the face, neck, orqangizdan, in the abdomen (belly) and your chest fat ' to collect the taking comes in. Also, your hands and your feet thin to be remains. That is in addition to, purple colored stretch marks and high blood pressure

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be can. These tumors bone also reduced push can.

Growth hormone-producing tumors.

This will generate a lot of growth hormone the tumor. In children, growth hormone stimulates the growth of all the bones in the body almost too much. When this happens, the results is called gigantism. The increased height Gigantizmga (more than 7 feet), to grow very quickly, include increased sweating, and pain in the joints. At adults too much growth hormone akromegali that that referred to the position causing produces. This is the following own into be taken can:

Skull, the additional growth in hands and feet

Thorough sound

Because of the face bones of additional growth in the face the appearance of a change

Facial bones of the growth due to teeth wide range

Birgul pain

Snoring or sleep apnea

Sugar diabetes or glucose tolerance disorders

Pituitary tumors what the reason is?

Experts in these neoplasms why the reason is that you do not know. But a condition that called a few endocrine neoplazi type I (men 1) your risk increase can. This condition families through pass.

What are the symptoms of pituitary tumors?

Semptomlar depends on the tumor type and the affected areas of the pituitary gland. The disruption of the pituitary hormones or very reason for many of these

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tumors can lead to symptoms. Everyone I alaatlar the difference be can.The symptoms of other health problems like seem can.Every time a diagnosis for health to maintain the provider to refer.

Pituitary tumor is determined by how much?

Your asks about your medical history and physical will host your medical staff. Should be one of these tests, you can:

Blood and urine tests.These tests, the level of hormones in blood and urine checks.

CT.Your body the picture of this test bodiesi create to an x-ray of the light and from the computer it uses.

The mdgs.MrThis test your body's organs and structures detailed images of creation for large magnetic, radio waves and a computer uses.

The biopsy.This test during the provider of tissue sample with a needle with or surgery during taken away.Then a microscope under checked.The biopsy, cancer or other abnormal cells in the presence of determine the will.

The pituitary tumor - how are treated?

Your health to maintain the provider on the basis of you to most of the best treatment to figure out is:

Young unlucky few

Your overall health and medical history

What kind of sick you are

Some drugs, treatments , or treatment of this methodrini how well you see you can

Not necessarily how many continue to be expected

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Your feedback or your advantage

The treatment following their into to be taken can:

Surgery, the tumor take away for. Surgery is often small tumors for a good opportunity.

External radiation (external beam therapy). This treatment is right cancer cells to radiation with high levels of sends. Treatment area of the surrounding tissue to protect to for a special shield from use you can. These treatments are painless and usually a few minutes, continue will.

Radiosurgery (stereotactic radiosurgery) or gamma knife treatment. This cancer tissue sent 1 high dose radiation uses. This near surrounding tissues, less damage will deliver. This is actually the surgery is not. But surgery is like, is it a tumor taking away 1-session treatment.

Tibbisefirlik.az Drug in different types of tumor by out carried how growth hormone control make to use a can.

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